

Author: Oluwafemi Agboola, PhD

Affiliation: Atiba University, Oyo, Nigeria

Email: [agboolaoluwafemi01@gmail.com/](mailto:agboolaoluwafemi01@gmail.com) oluwafemi.agboola@atibauniversity.edu.ng

ORCID: 0009-0005-5703-3326

Bachelor of Arts in History and International Studies, Master in Diplomacy and Strategic Studies, PhD in International Relations and Diplomacy

ARTICLES

1. Title:

Analysis on International Economic Relations between Romanian and Nigeria from 1966-2024.

2. Abstract:

To aid our understanding about the two countries under discourse, there is the need to take a cursory look into their historical backgrounds. The present Romanians exist as far back as 2million years ago. The originality of the cultural areas, related to the other European pre-historical cultures. This can be seen in the art of pottery (painted earthenware, clay statues such as the famous "thinker" of Hamangle Cernavoda). The Tertaria clay tables (incised pictographic motifs) attest to an early archaic writing among the first in Europe around 400BC, contemporary with the Sumerian writing. The descendants of those ancient civilizations were the Getodacians, who in the first century B.C founded the powerful kingdom of Dacia with its political and religious center at Sarmizegetusa, in present day Transylvania. In the early 2nd century A.D., the Roman imperial armies led by Emperor Trajan conquered Darcia (A.D. 106), turned it into Roman provinces and colonized it with Roman and Romanized people. Thus the Geto-Darcians got Romanized and the ethno genesis of the Romanian people was completed in the 7th century. Romania is a country located in Europe with its capital Bucharest. The Danube River flows in the south of the country. Romania is one of the Balkan countries located in the north of Balkans. Bucharest is the 12th largest city in Romania followed by Cluj-Napoca, Iasi, Timisoara, Constanta, Craiova, Brasov, and Galati. While Nigeria history was shrouded in obscurity though, this could be divided in line with these three phases viz: precolonial, colonial and post colonial era. Thus, Nigeria is located on the west coast of Africa and is the most populous black country in the world, bordering the North Atlantic Ocean, between Benin and Cameroon. Nigeria covers 356,668 square miles (923,7770 sq kilometers).

However, this paper seeks to discuss an analysis of International Economic Relations between Romania and Nigeria from 1966-2024 thus, the first part discusses the comparative analyses by delving into the core economic relations of the two countries, while further stresses the nexus that link both countries' foreign policy, the other part emphasises on the two countries' level of bilateral dealings coupled with the Romanian activities with the rest of other African countries; the paper equally raises some of the research questions that might arise in the course of this work and its methodologies in which later concludes with a logical conclusion.

3. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The International Economic Relations between Romania and Nigeria continued to exploring concrete sphere of economic activities interesting for both countries such as the following Viz: banking systems, tourism cooperation, agricultural development, high tech technologies, et.cetera. Hitherto, different aspects and analyses of economic, political and cultural bilateral Relations are ongoing and in a way fostering the relationship. This in a sense, fostering the relationship between Romania and Nigeria the more and constitutes a promise for re-launching a more traditional Romania diplomatic action towards Nigeria.

With a population of 22million, Romania is central Europe's second largest market. Romania boasts several real advantages an excellent location at the crossroads of the main trade route between western Europe and Asia between south Europe(the Mediterranean) and northern Europe. However, 1990s were marked by economic down turn for the Romania, worse in the first transition years(1990-1992), when the economy shrank by 27%, and over 1997-1999(a decline of over 12%). This trend ,accompanied by quasi-permanent inflation and a significant rise in unemployment, evolved on the backdrop of measures geared at decentralization, privatization and notably after 1997, accelerated economy restructuring. Thus, the interval 2000-2008 brought a remarked economic recovery with an annual growth rate above 6% higher over 2003-2008 when Romania posted a sizable rise in consumption and productive investment.

The GDP in Nigeria averaged 157.09USD Billion from 1960 until 2022, reaching an all time high of 574.18USD Billion in 2014 and a record low of 4.20USD Billion in 1960. Unlike the 1970s, a major feature of Nigeria's economy in the 1980s was its dependence on petroleum, which accounts for 87percent of exportation. However, Nigeria Economic real GDP growth fell to 3.3% in 2022 from 3.6% in 2021, precipitated mainly by a decline in oil production. Higher than expected deficits will start from Jan 1, 2024 as Nigeria's export of crude could not reach 1.7million per day.

Whilst as the world financial crisis erupted in autumn 2008 caused commercial and credit flows drop, 2009 and 2010 were years of economic downturn although the Romanian banking system is used and the economy grew for nearly one decade, Romanian still been affected by the

global economic and financial crisis, posting drops in GDP of 7% in 2009 and an estimated 2% in 2010 concurrently with an expanding budget deficits and unemployment. Foreign Direct Investment too declined in 2009, standing at about EUR4.5billion(roughly half the figure of the previous year). Thus,the government still aim to cushion the effects of the crisis were geared at stimulating economic growth, maintaining the capacity to attract investment and protecting the economic interests of the people by lowering the number of taxes included.

On the 22nd of August 2012,Prof.Dr.Anton Caragea director of Institute of International Relations and Economic Cooperation and H.E.Abba Abdullahi Tijani Ambassador of Federal Republic of Nigeria in Romania shed more light on why International Economic Relations should be continued between the two countries (the last meeting was held in 2001) with Romania to readapt mutual agreements to Romania states as an EU member country. The main area of bilateral cooperation were economy and culture for the future.

An agreement between the government of Romania and the government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria on the reciprocal promotion and protection of investments was adopted in 18 December 1998 while espoused by the parties involved in 3 June 2005,which has Article 1-11. The preamble of the article states interalia :

"The government of Romania and the government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria hereinafter referred to as "the contracting parties."

Desiring to intensify economic co-operation for the mutual benefits of both states, intending to create and maintain favourable conditions for investments by investors of one contracting party in the state territory of the other contracting party.

Recognizing the need to promote and protect foreign investments with the aim of fostering the economic prosperity of both states."

In 2022, Nigeria exported \$4.42M to Romanian. The main products exported from Nigeria to Romanian were Rubber(\$2.1m), polyacetals(\$789k), and other only seeds (\$683k). During the last 27 years the exports of Nigeria to Romanian have decreased at an annualized rate of 2.84%, from \$9.64m in 1995 to \$4.42m in 2022. Romanian equally had a large net trade with Nigeria in the exports of machine (12.8m), metals(\$5.55m), and transportation (\$3.98m). Moreso, Nigeria had a large net trade with Romania in the exports of plastic and rubbers(\$2.96m), vegetable products (\$749k), and wood products (615k). Another instance was when the Romania exported goods worth \$30.9m to Nigeria and this was in the area of products like valves(\$4.91m), Iron pipes(\$4.14m), and planes, helicopters, and spacecraft (\$3.2m). During the last 27 years the exports of Romania to Nigeria have increased at an annualized rate of 0.49% from \$27.1m in 1995 to \$30.9m in 2022.

Romanian has edge over Nigeria in that its macro-economics prospects have visibly improved of late, on the backdrop of external demand, though, unemployment related problems are likely to persist. Hence, Romanian accession to the OECD remains a priority of the Romania diplomacy. Likewise, Romania's roles as a donor state that improved its capacity to offer financial and technical assistance to some of the state in the Balkans and in the eastern neighborhood is an argument in favour of concerted action to promote and support regional economic and African development as a whole.

While economic of Romania is a complex high-income economy with a skilled labour force, ranked 12th in the European Union by total nominal GDP and 7th largest when adjusted by purchasing power parity. The world Bank notes that Romania's efforts are focused on accelerating structural reforms and strengthening institutions in order to further converge with the European Union. The country's economic growth has been one of the highest in the European Union since 2010 as it witnessed 2022 a better-than-expected 4.8% increase (1st of February 2024 est.) \$ 382.83 Billion (nominal, 2024 est.) \$ 780.8 Billion (PPP, 2023 est.)

While Nigeria early economy revolved around agriculture and wage labour. Today, Nigeria has the largest economy in Africa and one of the largest economies in the globe. While a lot of Nigeria's economy still revolves around agriculture, Nigeria has a mixed economy system which include a variety of private freedom, combined with centralized economic planning and government regulation. Nigeria is a member of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), and a major figure in African Union these major regional groups symbolise her potential and relevant economically.

In 2021, Nigeria ranked 126 in the Economic Complexity Index (ECI.7B). That same year, Romania ranked 26 in the Economic Complexity Index (ECI 1.07), and 42 in total exports (\$90.8B). Nigeria had a large net trade with Romania in the exports of plastic and rubbers (3.92m), vegetable products (\$801k), and chemical products (\$308k). During this year (2021), Romania

had a large net trade with Nigeria in the exports of minerals products (\$18.5m), machines(\$14.2m),and Transportation (\$3.43m).

Romanian interests in Nigeria from establishing a document of memorandum since 1968 signifies continuous diplomatic relations till date. This include the reciprocal visits of trade and economic delegation: Romania interests in Nigeria's oil and timber sectors; and the signing of an agreement on economic, scientific,and technical relations aid the relationship between the two countries the more.However,this also covers the unfavorable balance of trade between the two countries; Nigeria attempts to interests Romania in the import of groundnuts,oil,palm oil, cotton,and hides,and news that a group of Nigeria's Engineers are studying petroleum engineering in Romania triggered this.

I need to emphasize here that Romania is a developed country and is emerging to be a middle power in international affairs. Its economy ranks among the fastest growing in the European Union,being the world's 44th largest by nominal GDP,and the 36th largest by PPP. The sources of Romania income include the service industry had the largest share in the Romania gross domestic products in 2022, totalling 57.7percent.However, agriculture,forestry and fishing accounted for only 4.5% .

The question begging for answer in this respect is whether Nigeria is a developed or underdeveloped country? Well, according to the latest data by the UNDP, Nigeria ranks 161 out of 189 countries on the index, placing it in the category of low human development thus, Nigeria is a developing country categorized as lower lower middle income by the world bank. With the GDP estimated at \$4777billion in 2022, Nigeria is at the top of the ranking of the richest Africa countries, ahead of Egypt and South Africa. According to International Monetary Fund(IMF) growth projections ,this ranking should not experience any upheaval in the years to come as worldwide gross domestic product in 2022 was at about\$12,703USD per Capita. GDP in Nigeria on one hand,reached USD2,163 per Capita or 472.62billionUSD for the whole country while on the other,inflation in 2022 was around 18.85% thus, currently, Nigeria is ranked 32 of the major economies in the globe.

In contrast,the economy of Romania total by GDP and PPP makes her the wealthiest nation in south eastern Europe and is set to surpass Portugal and Poland if economic trends persists. Her economy is growing fast and future of the country looks promising. This means Romania is in top50 richest countries in the world. In 2023,in Europe, Romania is ranked on position 12 by GDP,and on position 7 by purchasing power parity (PPP). The country's economic growth has been one of the highest in the EU since 2010,it is expected to reach the EU average wealth by 2030. Thus,2020 economic analysis of the Romania and Nigeria indicated that Romania is richer than Nigeria for instance, Nigeria has a GDP per capita of \$4,900 as of 2020 while in Romania,the GDP per capita is \$28,800 as of 2020. However,in terms of the population

Romania's area is approximately 230,170km square (88,869square meter),while the Nigeria area is approximately 910,770km square (351,650square meter). This means Nigeria is 3.96 times bigger than Romania as of February 2024 Romania's population is 18.7million people- 208,683,379 fewer people than the population of Nigeria.

Nevertheless, Romania has a great advantage for the developing countries. It is the part of the most important economic club in the world,the EU. Another event of note in an effort to unify trade globally,was the Globe Chamber of Commerce and Industry roles who came up with a list of events that changed how African countries including Nigeria do business and thus this cannot be overemphasized nor de-emphasized.

Unveiling plans for Romania-Africa Economic Cooperation Forum in 2023, billed for Bucharest, Romania,the president of Globe Chamber of Commerce (GCCl),Hon.Buchi George ,the chairman said there are events lined in the 2023 and even beyond.

The Romania-Africa Economic Cooperation Forum 2023 is an Agric-Commerce,Agric-Business,Agric-Trade,and Agro-expert Programme distinct for creative minds, innovative thinkers and everyone with an interest in the Agricultural sector including: manufacturers,large scale farmers, exporters entrepreneurs, Business Moguls,State and Federal Government representatives amongst others.

The Agricultural program was a breaking ground for all Agro business and to unify international countries seeking to unlock new exports opportunities in Nigeria in particular and Africa in general where strong economic growth is driving demand for imported food and farm products. The event boosted bilateral trade ,open new doors of opportunities for global partnership,boosted economy growth and increase technological capacities.

It was indeed an opportunity for both countries to share useful information and developmental ideas channel towards building and expanding capacity. This event was a big one because Romania are working with African Organization and some European trade facilitators, knowing how much they contribute to the global trade these days. Hence,if things are easier and accessible on both ends,it will be very easy for both finished goods and raw materials to go either ways with little or no stress in 2023 and beyond.

4. Methodology and research questions

Romania-Nigeria comparison based on several hundred individual data items from dozens of different sources shall be explored.All data would based on the most recent and past available data to me. Primary, secondary and tertiary sources shall be employed within my research of 3-4years. Though,few historians have written on this topic and they have sought to expand our understanding of the subject matter however,the research will attempt to build upon their

works and form a more global and far reaching conclusion about the roles of the two countries in question and to analyse in details their economic relationship from 1966-2024.

The chief question I am seeking out to proffer answer to is to define and delineate the nature of the processes of the economic relationship from the earliest time till date.

I will begin my research by examining official documents printed materials by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Equally, I will then examine memoirs, and if possible I might travel home to Nigeria to conduct interview concerned groups or officials who at the helm of the affairs of the state during summer. How did Romania and Nigeria conceive of themselves before economic relation started between them?, what may explain their reactions to the growth and development of economic so far towards nation building?

History is an issue of legacy and legitimacy is directly linked to economic power, thus, I will rely heavily upon the collection of approximately letters between the two states such as memorandum of understanding, collections from Historical Society, the museum as well as the library of the Ovidius University of Constanta, Romania, Reporter's diaries.

Methodological holism shall be employed, this include theories, economic modelling, institutional analysis, data handling, estimation, inferences, interpretation, experiment, empirics, qualitative research, quantitative research, descriptive research, exploratory research, oral interviews of focus groups, case studies, cooperative analyses, multimedia and textual analysis, qualitative analysis tools, mixed-method research, experimental research shall be employed in the course of this research.

In the course of this work, I plan to examine the manifold ways in which the ideological prescriptions disseminated would be corrected and I equally plan to relate my investigation of the ways in which the youths responded to new ideas about white and black race relationship and to the new ideas about Romania -Nigeria economic relationship and to the Africa at large and to respond to sociologist, anthropologist and even the psychological theorists works on childhood and memory about nothing good in Africa. By examining the idea about selfhood lying and focusing on the ways in which the youths understood them and responded to them. I hope to challenge current understandings of the overarching roles of culture and ideology in post cold war era too.

Lastly, I will consider the works of journalists written at the inception of the economic relationship of the two countries till date. I have read so far extremely rich sources, raising a number of important questions of methodology. How far can we trust these reporters, who often wrote several years after the event they witnessed? Were their works little more than cases of special pleading or fact? All these and many more shall be employed.

Conclusion

The above explicit various economic relationship of the Romania and Nigeria in which are not limited to the above. A comparative analyses have been deduced and few years had established wide relations of collaboration with the developing countries, viewing this is not only as increase in Romania contribution towards the economic and social development of Africa countries in which Nigeria is not excluded, but also as mutually advantageous economically. International Economic Relations with developing countries including African countries have shown a constant upward trend. Thus, in the 1961-1970 decade, Romanian commercial exchange with developing countries have increased by 4.9 times rising at an average annual rate of 17.3 per cent. This rate is considerably higher than that of the country's foreign trade in general, since commerce with the developing countries constitutes the fastest growing flow during that period. Consequently, the share of developing countries in Romania's foreign trade has grown year by year.

The above also apply in full to Romania's commercial relations with the African countries. The 1971, the volume of countries grew tremendously. The Romania- Nigeria relationship has the ability to become an example of building an economic and cultural exchange area between Africa and Romania, remarked Prof. Anton Caragea. Therefore, auspicious moment for reconstructing and rebuilding the framework of dialogue and friendship between Romania and Nigeria as the level of bilateral expectation is greater and the political and economic desire for such a favourable expansion of activities would be marked clearly and this is an appropriate note in which to conclude.

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